

FREQUENCY OF HYPERTENSION IN METABOLIC DYSFUNCTION ASSOCIATED STEATOTIC LIVER DISEASE PATIENTS

Dr Rabiya Illyas^{*1}, Dr Kanwal Dilshad², Dr Tazeen Nazar³,
Dr Muhammad Abrar⁴, Dr Haseeb Ashraf⁵

^{*1,2}Postgraduate resident Medicine, East Medical ward Mayo Hospital, Lahore

³Associate professor of Medicine, East Medical ward Mayo Hospital, Lahore

⁴Medical officer THQ Hospital, Depalpur, Okara

⁵Postgraduate resident Gastroenterology, Lahore general Hospital, Lahore

^{*1}rabiyaillias70@gmail.com

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17731594>

Keywords

Metabolic dysfunction-associated steatotic liver disease, Hypertension, Obesity, Diabetes mellitus, Dyslipidemia

Article History

Received: 22 June 2025

Accepted: 26 July 2025

Published: 01 August 2025

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Corresponding Author: *

Dr Rabiya Illyas

Abstract

Background: Metabolic dysfunction-associated steatotic liver disease (MASLD) is one of the most prevalent chronic liver disorders worldwide and is closely linked with components of the metabolic syndrome such as obesity, diabetes mellitus, and dyslipidemia. **Objective:** To determine the frequency of hypertension in patients with metabolic dysfunction associated steatotic liver disease (MASLD). **Methodology:** This cross-sectional study was conducted in the Department of General Medicine, King Edward Medical University/Mayo Hospital, Lahore, from 13th January, 2025 to 13th June, 2025. A total of 96 MASLD patients aged 18–80 years were enrolled through non-probability consecutive sampling. Demographic data including age, gender, BMI, smoking history, diabetes mellitus, and dyslipidemia were recorded. All patients underwent abdominal ultrasonography to confirm MASLD. **Results:** The mean age of participants was 48.6 ± 11.2 years; 58.3% were males and 41.7% females. The mean BMI was 29.8 ± 4.6 kg/m². Hypertension was present in 46 patients (47.9%). The prevalence of hypertension was significantly higher among males (55.4%), obese individuals (63.0%), diabetics (70.6%), and those with dyslipidemia (69.2%) ($p < 0.05$ for all). Increasing age and male gender were also significantly associated with hypertension. **Conclusion:** It is concluded that hypertension is highly prevalent among patients with MASLD, reflecting the shared metabolic pathways between hepatic steatosis and cardiovascular dysfunction. Male gender, obesity, diabetes, and dyslipidemia were significant predictors of hypertension.

INTRODUCTION

Metabolic dysfunction associated steatotic liver disease (MASLD) is the most common chronic liver disease. Hepatic steatosis occurs without significant alcohol consumption or other secondary causes which leads within the hepatocytes to fat accumulation. As

of today, MASLD is considered a significant public health concern [1]. MASLD include a number of liver conditions such as simple steatosis, metabolic dysfunction associated steato-hepatitis, fibrosis, cirrhosis, and liver cancer [2]. Progression to chronic

liver disease was believed to be rare and benign, however steato-hepatitis may progress and result with significant morbidity and mortality [3]. The global prevalence of MASLD is estimated to be 25.24% with the Middle East and South America ranging as the highest and Africa the lowest. In Western countries MASLD prevalence is reported to be 15-40%, while in Asian countries it is 9-40%. Most recently, Asia has been estimated to be 29.6%, suggesting it may have surpassed the western countries [4]. The primary causes of MASLD include obesity, which is present in 40% or more of the patients, diabetes mellitus, and hypertriglyceridemia with 20% or more of the cases, associated with insulin resistance of metabolic syndrome. Of particular importance is the presence of hypertension which is a significant comorbidity in MASLD patients [5]. These include chronic low-grade inflammation, oxidative stress, damage to the blood vessel lining, and activation of the renin-angiotensin-aldosterone system. Having too much visceral fat as well as having insulin resistance triggers the release of fat and proinflammatory cytokines such as TNF- α and IL-6 [6]. These cytokines cause the blood vessels to malfunction and retain sodium, leading to high blood pressure. In addition, insulin resistant liver MAS is associated with increased SNS activity and vasoconstriction, and issues with vasodilation related to nitric oxide. This helps explain the link between MASLD and other hypertensive disorders. It is not a coincidence that the prevalence of HTN has increased in the last two decades in parallel with that of obesity and type 2 diabetes [7]. Increased fat in hepatocytes is a result of a combination of insulin resistance, lipotoxicity, and changes in the gut microbiota and is associated with increased complications in the liver and other parts of the body (extrahepatic complications) [8]. MASLD, as shown in several epidemiological studies, is associated with increased risk of HTN, CVD, and liver cancer, as well as other diseases (diabetes, chronic kidney disease, and chronic lung disease) [9]. It can also lead to higher all-cause mortality. Hypertension co-occurring with metabolic dysfunction steatotic liver disease presents implications on the micro and macro public health domain, and the overall burden on non-communicable disease (NCD) in the landscape of Pakistan especially resource-poor settings- is exacerbated [10]. This is in part due to the difficulties

in management which arise because steatotic liver disease, and vascular comorbidities are intertwined in a warped cycle [11].

Objective

The aim of this study is to determine the frequency of HTN in patients with metabolic dysfunction associated steatotic liver disease. In view of the significant global burden of HTN and its intrinsic link with metabolic dysfunction associated steatotic liver disease, it is necessary to clarify the role of MASLD control in affecting the prognosis of HTN.

Methodology

This cross-sectional study was conducted at Department of General Medicine, KEMU/Mayo Hospital, Lahore from 13th January, 2025 to 13th June, 2025. Sample size of 96 patients is estimated by using 95% confidence level, 10% absolute precision with expected percentage age prevalence of HTN in MASLD patients as 45.65%. Data were collected through Non-probability consecutive sampling.

Inclusion criteria:

1. Patients aged 18-80 years.
2. Both genders.
3. Patients with MASLD fulfilling the criteria of MASLD defined in operational definition.

Exclusion criteria:

1. Pregnant females.
2. Patients with renal, cardiovascular, or hepatic disease.
3. Patients with drug-induced fatty liver disease (e.g., synthetic estrogens, salicylates, tamoxifen).

Data Collection

Following approval from the Institutional Ethical Review Committee of King Edward Medical University, eligible patients meeting the inclusion criteria were recruited from the medical outpatient department of Mayo Hospital, Lahore. Informed written consent was obtained from all participants prior to enrollment. Demographic and clinical information including age, gender, body mass index (BMI), diabetes mellitus status, smoking habits, and dyslipidemia was recorded using a pre-designed

structured proforma. All participants underwent abdominal ultrasonography (USG) for confirmation of MASLD as per the operational definition. Patients diagnosed with MASLD were managed according to standard institutional protocols. All data were documented systematically in the pre-designed proforma to ensure uniformity and minimize bias during data collection.

Data Analysis

All gathered information was inputted and analyzed via SPSS version 26. Age and BMI were analyzed as quantitative variables and described as mean ± standard deviation (SD). Variables considering gender, diabetes mellitus, smoking status, dyslipidemia, and hypertension were described as qualitative variables and summarized as proportions and percentages. Data were stratified based on the possible confounding variables which included age,

gender, BMI, smoking status, diabetes mellitus, and dyslipidemia to determine possible effect on the frequency of hypertension in MASLD patients. Post-stratification, the chi-square test was conducted, and a p-value of <0.05 was regarded as statistically significant.

Results

Data were collected from 96 patients, with a mean age of 48.6 ± 11.2 years. Among them, 56 (58.3%) were male and 40 (41.7%) were female. The mean BMI was 29.8 ± 4.6 kg/m², showing that most patients were overweight or obese. A total of 28 (29.2%) participants had a history of smoking, 34 (35.4%) had diabetes mellitus, and 39 (40.6%) had dyslipidemia. Overall, 46 (47.9%) patients were hypertensive, indicating that nearly half of MASLD patients had coexisting elevated blood pressure.

Table 1. Baseline Demographic and Clinical Characteristics of MASLD Patients (n = 96)

Variable	n (%) / Mean ± SD
Age (years)	48.6 ± 11.2
Gender	
• Male	56 (58.3%)
• Female	40 (41.7%)
BMI (kg/m ²)	29.8 ± 4.6
Smoking history	28 (29.2%)
Diabetes mellitus	34 (35.4%)
Dyslipidemia	39 (40.6%)
Hypertension	46 (47.9%)

In the group studied, 55.4% of the 31 males had hypertension compared to 37.5% of the 15 females, (p = 0.04). The age variable seemed to have the strongest relation; of the 31 patients aged 18-40, only 9 had hypertension whereas 26 of the 50 patients aged 41-60 and 11 of the 16 patients above 60 had hypertension (p = 0.02). Patients with obesity (BMI > 30 kg/m²) had the highest

prevalence of hypertension (29 patients 63.0%) (p = 0.01). 24 (70.6%) of the diabetic patients studied also had hypertension and 27 (69.2%) of those with dyslipidemia also had hypertension (p = 0.002 and p = 0.01, respectively). Smokers had a greater percentage of hypertension (60.7%) compared to non-smokers, however, the association was not significant (p = 0.09).

Table 2. Distribution of Hypertension According to Demographic and Metabolic Factors

Variable	Hypertensive n (%)	Normotensive n (%)	p-value
Gender			
• Male	31 (55.4%)	25 (44.6%)	0.04 *
• Female	15 (37.5%)	25 (62.5%)	

Age Group (years)			
• 18-40	9 (29.0%)	22 (71.0%)	0.02 *
• 41-60	26 (52.0%)	24 (48.0%)	
• >60	11 (68.8%)	5 (31.2%)	
BMI > 30 kg/m ²	29 (63.0%)	17 (37.0%)	0.01 *
Diabetes Mellitus	24 (70.6%)	10 (29.4%)	0.002 *
Dyslipidemia	27 (69.2%)	12 (30.8%)	0.01 *
Smoking	17 (60.7%)	11 (39.3%)	0.09

*Statistically significant at p < 0.05 (Chi-square test).

Among obese patients (BMI > 30 kg/m²), 63.0% were hypertensive (p = 0.01). Diabetic patients had the highest prevalence, with 70.6% showing hypertension (p = 0.002), while dyslipidemia was present in 69.2% of hypertensive cases (p = 0.01).

Hypertension was also more frequent among males (55.4%) and patients aged over 60 years (68.8%) with respective p-values of 0.04 and 0.02. Smoking again showed a non-significant relationship (60.7%, p = 0.09).

Table 3. Association Between Hypertension and Metabolic Risk Factors in MASLD

Risk Factor	Present (n)	Hypertensive (%)	p-value
Obesity (BMI > 30 kg/m ²)	46	63.0	0.01 *
Diabetes Mellitus	34	70.6	0.002 *
Dyslipidemia	39	69.2	0.01 *
Smoking	28	60.7	0.09
Age > 60 years	16	68.8	0.02 *
Male Gender	56	55.4	0.04 *

*Statistically significant at p < 0.05.

The mean systolic blood pressure was 136.4 ± 15.2 mmHg, and the mean diastolic pressure was 86.3 ± 8.6 mmHg, reflecting an overall hypertensive trend in the cohort. The mean fasting blood glucose level was 122.5 ± 31.4 mg/dL, while triglycerides averaged 186.7 ± 48.2 mg/dL. Mean total cholesterol was 201.3 ± 42.5 mg/dL, HDL cholesterol was 41.7 ± 6.9

mg/dL, and LDL cholesterol was 128.9 ± 32.7 mg/dL, showing a dyslipidemic pattern consistent with metabolic dysfunction. Liver enzymes were mildly elevated, with ALT 61.2 ± 21.4 U/L and AST 54.8 ± 19.7 U/L, indicating hepatic involvement associated with MASLD.

Table 4. Clinical and Biochemical Characteristics of MASLD Patients (n = 96)

Parameter	Mean ± SD / n (%)
Systolic Blood Pressure (mmHg)	136.4 ± 15.2
Diastolic Blood Pressure (mmHg)	86.3 ± 8.6
Fasting Blood Glucose (mg/dL)	122.5 ± 31.4
Serum Triglycerides (mg/dL)	186.7 ± 48.2
Total Cholesterol (mg/dL)	201.3 ± 42.5
HDL Cholesterol (mg/dL)	41.7 ± 6.9
LDL Cholesterol (mg/dL)	128.9 ± 32.7
ALT (U/L)	61.2 ± 21.4

AST (U/L)	54.8 ± 19.7
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Among patients with BMI < 25 kg/m², 4 (28.6%) were hypertensive, compared to 13 (36.1%) in those with BMI 25–30 kg/m², and 29 (63.0%) in patients with BMI > 30 kg/m² (p = 0.03). Diabetes was strongly associated, with 24 (70.6%) hypertensive diabetics versus 22 (35.5%) hypertensive non-diabetics (p = 0.002). Likewise, 27 (69.2%) of dyslipidemic patients

had hypertension compared with 19 (33.3%) without dyslipidemia (p = 0.01). Although smokers had a higher proportion of hypertension (17, 60.7%) than non-smokers (29, 42.6%), the difference did not reach significance (p = 0.09).

Table 5. Stratified Frequency of Hypertension by Clinical and Metabolic Variables (n = 96)

Variable	Total (n)	Hypertensive n (%)	Normotensive n (%)	p-value
BMI < 25 kg/m ²	14	4 (28.6%)	10 (71.4%)	0.03 *
BMI 25–30 kg/m ²	36	13 (36.1%)	23 (63.9%)	
BMI > 30 kg/m ²	46	29 (63.0%)	17 (37.0%)	
Diabetes Mellitus	34	24 (70.6%)	10 (29.4%)	0.002 *
No Diabetes Mellitus	62	22 (35.5%)	40 (64.5%)	
Dyslipidemia Present	39	27 (69.2%)	12 (30.8%)	0.01 *
No Dyslipidemia	57	19 (33.3%)	38 (66.7%)	
Smoking	28	17 (60.7%)	11 (39.3%)	0.09
Non-Smoking	68	29 (42.6%)	39 (57.4%)	

*Statistically significant at p < 0.05.

Discussion

The present study evaluated the frequency of hypertension among patients with MASLD and found that almost half (47.9%) of the patients studied had hypertension. This result is in line with previous global studies that found between 45 and 50 percent of patients with MASLD had hypertension as well. The condition is now recognized as a multisystem metabolic disorder with its progression intricately linked with other key components of the metabolic syndrome along with hypertension; namely, insulin resistance, chronic low-grade inflammation, and endothelial dysfunction. The metabolic syndrome with these conditions in MASLD strongly supports and suggests that hypertension is not merely a comorbidity of MASLD, but rather a condition that is interdependent with MASLD. Insulin resistance also drives other hypertension mechanisms, including vascular stiffening, sympathetic nervous system activation, and sodium retention [12]. Likewise, hypertensive mechanisms also arise due to hepatic steatosis through inflammation and alterations of the

RAAS. Our results showed that greater incidences of hypertension occurred in males, older age groups,

people with obesity, as well as those with diabetes mellitus and dyslipidemia. Observations made in your research has drawn similar conclusions. For example, Chew and others noted that 49.5% of MASLD patients also had hypertension, and similar metabolic risk factors were noted. Also, Chan described that being male, having obesity, and diabetes were MASLD strongest predictors of hypertension [13]. It shows mechanisms that are similar in both liver and blood vessel disease. The increasing prevalence of obesity and metabolic syndrome in Pakistan are likely to worsen the situation. This calls for the immediate and integrated management of conditions in primary care and hepatology clinics. The study participants also had an average BMI of 29.8 ± 4.6 kg/m², also showing a predominance of overweight individuals. Obesity-associated viscerally deposited and ectopic fat, along with the other adipokine dysregulation is clinically known to worsen steatosis of the liver and disease of

the blood vessels [14]. In addition, the study showed that 35% of participants had diabetes, and 40% had dyslipidemia. Dyslipidemia and these other conditions are known to worsen hypertension and atherosclerosis. This demonstrates that MASLD is a metabolic “hub” where the dysfunction of the liver and the heart meet. The connection of dyslipidemia and hypertension in MASLD also shows a clinically meaningful connection and an absence of explanation [15-17]. Accruing fats in the liver can disrupt the body’s ability to metabolize lipids, which causes an increase in triglycerides, a decrease in HDL, promotes arterial stiffness, and dysfunctions the endothelium. Age was observed to be the most important determinant for hypertension in this group with the most patients within the age group of 60 and above. Reduced compliance of the aged blood vessels along with increased oxidative stress and other cumulative metabolic damage might explain this mechanism [18]. The reasoning for this demographic enhances hypertension, especially for men, has been explained with hormonal differences, particularly visceral fat and lifestyle behaviors encompassing greater alcohol and tobacco use. The public health consequences of this are considerable. Adjusting lifestyle to prevent MASLD and hypertension should be considered [19]. There is an epidemiologic transition in Pakistan and it should be targeted for the preventable non-communicable diseases. There is a need for MASLD patients to have regular hypertension screenings, especially in the obese, diabetic, and dyslipidemic segments of the population. The focused and systematic assessment of both metabolic and hepatic parameters in this population is the study’s most considerable strength. But it should have less focus on a singular population, which is a restriction that should be considered in this study. A cross-sectional design limits causal inference, and having only one study center may limit generalizability. Also, not checking fasting insulin and HOMA-IR indices limits insights into insulin resistance. Regardless, the prevalence and associations are within the range of strong evidence from the global literature, which boosts the findings’ credibility.

Conclusion

It is concluded that hypertension is highly prevalent among patients with metabolic dysfunction-

associated steatotic liver disease (MASLD), affecting nearly half of the studied population. The connection between the metabolic system and cardiovascular system is evident from the association between hepatic steatosis and systemic hypertension. This association is clear with the understanding that the combination of these conditions relates to the broader scope of metabolic syndrome which is multifaceted and complex due to the presence of insulin resistance, obesity, and chronic inflammation dyslipidemia. It was further noted that hypertension occurred disproportionately to older age, male sex, as well as the presence of obesity, diabetes mellitus, and dyslipidemia. This reinforces the understanding that patients with MASLD represent high target syndrome with the need of prioritized assessment for not only the liver pathology but also the likely associated cardiovascular diseases.

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